

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING MEDIA EDUCATION LITERACY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7729476>

Abstract. *In the article, pedagogical aspects of information literacy formation based on the media education environment, the place of our growing youth in society, the relevance of the formation of media culture, media education tools, types, and their use in the educational process were discussed and scientific proposals were given.*

Keywords: *media, sound, literacy, writing, newspaper, media education tools, types, magazine, lithography, educational process, telegraph, telephone, voice recording, pedagogical skills, television, computer, Internet.*

It would not be an exaggeration to say that the large-scale reforms carried out by our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev are aimed at the prospect, peace and prosperity of our country. One of the most important tasks is the upbringing of intellectual youth striving for a goal that links the national development and prosperity of our republic with their life activities and future.

In our country, much attention is paid to the field of media education in order to improve people's living conditions, provide education to young people, meaningful organization of their free time and, as a result, active participation in society, instilling positive emotions, such as love for family, profession, country.

Therefore, special importance is attached to all areas related to the development of society. In the conditions of modernizing Uzbekistan, at the level of state policy, attention is paid to young people, and the intellectual potential and way of thinking of young people are changing day by day in a positive direction in the process of science, education and production.

In this regard, the following comments of the leader of our Dalat are relevant: "We will continue the state policy towards youth without any deviations, not only continue it, but also raise this policy to the high level required by today's time.

" We are mobilizing all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that young people can become independent thinkers, have a high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people equal to their peers in any field, and be happy" [1]. Proper use of information provided by the media and other sources of information enables people to understand their information needs, find and own information, and evaluate its quality.

The term "information" has many definitions. "Computer - (English computer - I calculate) - an automatic device that works according to a predetermined program (program).

Same term as electronic calculator (ECV). However, in addition to performing computer calculations, its functions are much wider. Several generations of computers can be shown in the development of an ES. These generations differ from each other in the types of elements, design and technological features, logical structure, software, technical details, ease of use of technology.

Modern youth strive to think in a new way and keep up with the times. Its basis is intellect. The rapid development of computer technology is becoming increasingly important in human thinking. It is difficult to imagine our age, which is called the age of information, without telecommunications.

The latest phones, tablets, laptops and computers are happy to find the information and news we need instantly via the Internet. Nowadays, we can get the information we need from sites on the Internet in a few minutes. For us it is very convenient, simple and saves time.

As we all know, our life today is unimaginable without the Internet. As a result of the rapid development of the Internet around the world, it has become possible not only to receive and distribute information, but also to do great things. Through the Internet, people can easily see and talk to distant friends and relatives, as well as send messages to each other.

I think one example is enough to illustrate. A simple schoolboy has to go to the library to complete the task, find the necessary books there and sit there for two or three hours, reading and writing in notebooks. Doing the same online at home has many benefits.

So that the student does not go to the library, does not spend time there, it will be possible to read the necessary information on the Internet and perceive it as information. Another example: in the past, if a person wanted to write a letter to a loved one, he had to take a pen and paper to write the letter, write words on it, and take it to the post office.

It will take a few days for the postman to pick it up and deliver it to the right place. Nowadays, such things have become commonplace. These things can be done in five minutes with a web remote control.

There are many such examples. Thus, the number of Internet users is increasing day by day, and many countries are advancing in the use of the Internet. Experts who polled fifty thousand people in forty-six countries concluded that Internet users in the Middle East, as well as in China, surpassed the population of developed countries in this regard. According to surveys, fifty-five percent of the population of Egypt and Saudi Arabia live buried in the Internet.

No European country made it into the top ten. Residents of developed countries mostly communicate with their friends on the Internet. And in South America, the Middle East and China, users spend more than five hours a week on social media.

The remaining four hours are spent sending emails. In developed countries, on the contrary, the main attention is paid to communication by e-mail. Malaysians are the largest social media users, with an average of over two hundred and thirty "online friends" per user.

The place after Malaysia is occupied by the Brazilians. Everything has its pros and cons. In addition to useful information, malicious obscene, corrupt information is also widely distributed on the Internet. The number of sites that promote prostitution, immorality and immorality, affecting the spirituality of a person, is increasing.

Some people deceive each other on the Internet, slander each other, many young families get divorced because of this, etc. Through the Internet, not only moral violations are committed, but also many crimes in the political, economic, financial and many other areas.

The above statements show that we can use the Internet for both good and bad. Our duty is to use it only for good. To do this, we need to establish patterns of Internet use based on the general teachings of our religion. First of all, a person who wants to use the Internet must correctly formulate the intention. Only then will this work be useful.

Before using the Internet, it is worth thinking about not wasting time in vain, that every minute counts. Before going online, you need to carefully prepare a work plan. It is also harmful to sit on the Internet for a long time, because of which a person can get sick with certain diseases.

In addition, all information viewed, heard and read on the Internet must be permitted by Shariah. But, unfortunately, some people visiting the site see things on the site that they don't see in real life.

They may think to themselves, "This job is not at the level of life." In fact, there is a flaw in the moral level of those who see these unthinkable works on the site. Therefore, one should not forget that God watches over him when he does everything.

Because Allah Almighty says in Sura Ghafir: "He knows the deceit of the eyes and what the breasts hide" (ayat 19). There is nothing that Allah does not know. He knows everything. He even knows what he has hidden in his heart without telling anyone. After that, there is no doubt about knowing other things. Let people know this.

You should start working on the Internet with "Bismillahir Rahmanir Rohim" and read as much as you know from the prayers that are read at the beginning of work. It is the duty of a true Muslim to fully respect the spiritual and educational rights of the site owners.

It is not possible to use the Internet of an office or another person without permission. Children's use of the Internet and computers must be managed wisely and carefully.

Family and upbringing have a great influence on the formation of the epistemological point of view of the child. They have a significant impact on how students process information and readiness to critically analyze knowledge. When students are confronted with conflicting information, teachers should guide them to seek information from a variety of sources.

This, in turn, allows students to evaluate new information based on existing knowledge and form their own point of view. Also, teachers should be able to convey to students the idea that there can be more than one correct answer to one question.

Today's youth are often referred to as "natives of the digital world". Their media skills are considered to be more developed than those of teachers. Such a generalization does not take into account the difference in media literacy among individual students, which, in turn, can be quite large.

Although the use of media and media content is a natural and normal process for most students, all children have the opportunity to use media outside of school. In addition, media skills do not develop on their own without a focused training process.

The concept of "media information literacy" is understood as a set of various skills necessary for a person to understand the world around him in the 21st century. Media and information literacy is inextricably linked to the role and functions of the media and other media such as libraries, archives and the Internet in our personal lives and in the life of a democratic society.

It helps to realize the human right to freely communicate and express one's opinion, to seek, receive and exchange ideas and information. Media and information literacy makes it possible to assess the media and other information providers and evaluate the role of the target audience based on the information available about what the media and other information providers produce, what messages they disseminate.

Media and information literate people acquire the following skills:

- a good understanding of the impact of the media and the forms of information presented through them;
- adoption of marital independent decisions;
- obtaining new information about the environment;

- contribute to the formation of a sense of community;
- support for collective discourse;
- continuous education throughout life;
- creation of information;
- critical thinking;
- self-presentation in the media and use for creative purposes;
- use the media in a manner that ensures personal safety and respect for social responsibility;
- active participation in the life of a democratic society and the global information network.

Forms and means of media expression are constantly evolving. Therefore, media and information literacy skills need to be constantly improved. Every teacher can be a media educator, giving their students the skills they need to live in a media culture.

The variety of approaches that teachers are exploring to use media education in their work has a number of advantages. The more diverse types of media that teachers introduce their students to, the richer and deeper media education becomes.

Today, the greatest challenge facing educators is to teach children and young people to navigate the sea of information. However, the formation of media and information literacy is no different from any other type of education: it is based on work with students.

A young teacher does not need to be a master of media culture, does not need to be a technical genius, but he must be able to give advice, based on his own life experience, on issues related to network etiquette.

The teacher should begin working with the media by thinking about his own relationship with the media: how do I use the media? How will they affect my work? The qualification of a media literacy teacher is based on personal skills in working with media, experience and interest in media, willingness to discuss various aspects of media literacy, and active participation in educational activities.

The media literacy educator does not judge the correctness of students' opinions or tastes in media, but uses them as a starting point for discussion. The media literacy educator must shape the experience of his young students, even if they are young; provides students with sufficient information and skills to learn how to protect themselves from the harmful effects of the media.

Although young people, especially urban youth, have been accustomed to the use of technology in their daily lives since childhood, today's youth are the first generation to experience this phenomenon.

They have an innate ability to interact with the media and perceive their surroundings as if it were just another Internet application. Therefore, while providing technical equipment and access to the Internet, it is also necessary to provide guidance on the safe and proper use of the media.

It is necessary to put things in order in the formation of media education literacy in the minds of the future generation and constantly monitor them. In such cases, children should not be left unattended.

The computer and telephone equipment they use must be constantly monitored. Because a child can learn about various pornographic sites from friends or acquaintances on the street and use them. Games that a child plays on the Internet or on a computer should enlighten the mind and cultivate good manners. So that their time is not wasted, parents must constantly act.

If a parent constantly teaches and controls the child how to use the Internet, then the modesty and manners of the child will be in place. He does not follow other people's ideas. The ability to think is well developed.

People born today are used to using media differently than previous generations. All generations have access to digital media, but those born at the beginning of the 21st century cannot imagine a world without media. It is difficult to assess the real influence of the media, as it is gradually increasing, since at this age the formation of consciousness and worldview takes place, and the media influences young people more than older people.

Adults do not always understand the reason for this influence, for example, the influence of social networks on the development of adolescents, including the formation of ideas about themselves that differ from the views of parents, as well as the formation of gender and gender identity during adolescence and adolescence.

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